

A CASE STUDY ON SUKHUAPADA CRAFTS VILLAGE – AN INDIGENOUS LIVING MUSEUM

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Abstract

Sukhuapada Crafts Village, located in Odisha, is a unique example of an indigenous living museum where traditional crafts are preserved and showcased within the community. This village is renowned for its exclusive range of crafts made on local stone, reflecting a rich cultural heritage passed down through generations. Unlike conventional museums, Sukhuapada offers an immersive experience where visitors can observe artisans at work and participate in hands-on training, providing a deeper understanding of the techniques and cultural significance of the crafts. The crafts serve not only as a source of livelihood for the artisans but also as a medium for expressing cultural narratives and maintaining community identity. This case study highlights the importance of preserving traditional crafts as a means of cultural preservation and economic development, offering valuable insights for similar communities worldwide. It further elucidates the avenues of research and education in this locality, community and the indigenous knowledge system in the aspect of museology.

Keywords: *Sukhuapada, Odisha, Crafts village, Living Museum, Indigenous crafts.*

Introduction

Sukhuapada is an ancient crafts village in Darpana Tehsil, Jajpur District of Odisha. It is located within the vicinity of an ancient archaeological settlement dating to the post-Mauryan period. This settlement is on the foothills and slope of Parabhadi hill; part of a natural Khondalite hill formation; Nandapahad or Lalitagiri. Lalitagiri is a world-famous Buddhist settlement of early historical Odisha with a cultural sequence; Post-Mauryan, Kushana, Gupta, and Bhaumakara periods. The brick and stone structural remains including several rare sculptures of Buddha, Bodhisattva, Tara, Maitreyi etc., defines a wide range of Buddhist settlement in this locality in the early 6th - 7th century C.E. (Patnaik, 2016). Hieun Tsang has mentioned about the diamond triangle of Buddhism in his travel itinerary which is identified as the modern-day hillocks; Udayagiri, Ratnagiri, and Lalitagiri of Odisha. All these three hillocks have Buddhist settlements with fine members of sculptural art (Mukherjee, 1957).

Historical Background

Odisha has been famous for its art and crafts since ancient times. Art is a medium of expression of human cognitive development and skill and requires a certain level of evolved techniques and technology. The people who create art can be termed as artisans and craftsmen etc., which in Odia language are called *kalākār*, *śilpi*, *bindhani*, *moharāna* and *kārigar* etc. (Mohanty, 2019). Historically we have evidence of different types of artisans and their hierarchy

mentioned in manuscripts and traditional texts. The major classifications of traditional artisans in Odisha are, *Śthapati* (architect or chief engineer), *Sūtragrahina* (engineer), *Bardhanika* (stone cutters) and *Takśaka* (sculptors) (Dey, 2016). These traditional terms for the artisans are still used in Odisha and the artisans of Sukhuapada village claim themselves as *maharāna* and keep their surname as Maharana.

Sculptural art in Odisha is globally popular for its intricate detailing and expressive aesthetics since historic times is as evident from the Mauryan monolith elephant at Dhauri to the Konark Sun temple, the artistic works have seen its gradual growth and reached zenith in due time. The artisans and the craftsmanship behind these marvels and beautiful creations need to be celebrated and promoted more globally to enrich and embrace our incredible and rich cultural heritage.

Sukhuapada – Crafts village

The existing village Sukhuapada is located on the south-eastern and eastern slope of the Parabhadi hill spreading up to the foothill of Olasuni hill. It is covered with khondalite boulders and sparse green vegetation. It presently consists of approximately 540 families out of which 300 are working on stone carvings and sculptural art. Most of these families are working over generations. They believe that their ancestors comprise the legacy of working on the major monumental architectures of Odisha since the early medieval period and they are following their footsteps forward. Many families in Odisha remain closely connected to the prominent temples in the region and are invited to participate in the annual festivals of Puri Jagannath Dham and Kendrapada Baldevji Mandir, among others. Additionally, 150 sculptors from this village contributed to the pillar carvings of the newly constructed Ayodhya Ram Mandir (The Times of India, 2023).

Indigenous Living Museum

An Indigenous Living Museum is a dynamic, community-driven institution that serves as both a repository and a living expression of Indigenous culture, heritage, and knowledge. One of the key features of an Indigenous Living Museum is its focus on intangible cultural heritage, which includes oral traditions, rituals, performances, and traditional knowledge systems. These elements are often transmitted through generations and are integral to the identity and continuity of Indigenous cultures. By prioritizing these aspects, Indigenous Living Museums challenge the conventional museum paradigm that often prioritizes tangible artefacts over intangible cultural expressions. This shift is crucial in addressing the historical marginalization and misrepresentation of Indigenous cultures in mainstream museums (Kreps, 2013).

Indigenous Living Museums are characterized by their emphasis on community involvement and self-representation. Indigenous communities are not just subjects of exhibition but active participants in the museum's operations, including decision-making processes, content creation, and interpretation. This participatory approach fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment among Indigenous peoples, allowing them to control how their culture is portrayed and ensuring that their perspectives are accurately represented (Peers & Brown, 2003).

This concept of an 'Indigenous living museum' in the context of Sukhuapada village orbits around the idea of preserving traditional crafts in their authentic form, within the community that has nurtured them. Unlike conventional museums, where artefacts are displayed in isolation, Sukhuapada showcases its cultural heritage through the daily lives and activities of its residents. Visitors can observe artisans at work (Fig.1), participate and gain a deeper understanding of the techniques and significance of various crafts. Further, the local artisans are welcoming in teaching their intricate crafting and carving techniques (Fig.2) to school students and fine art enthusiasts. This village is under consideration for the 'Crafts Village' scheme proposed by the Union Ministry of Textile in 2018 (The New Indian Express, 2022). The tradition of making stone carving and sculpting in this village has become a cultural continuum since 7th century C.E. which gives us multiple avenues in museum education and research as an example of 'Indigenous Living Museum.'

Cultural Significance

a. Preservation of Heritage

The crafts of Sukhuapada are not merely products; they are embodiments of the region's cultural heritage. Each craft item reflects the community's history, beliefs, and social practices, making them invaluable cultural artefacts. Traditional techniques, motifs, and materials used in these crafts have been meticulously preserved and passed down through generations, ensuring that the heritage remains intact. The preservation of these crafts ensures that the intangible cultural heritage of Sukhuapada is maintained for future generations, allowing them to connect with their roots and understand the historical context of their community.

b. Community Identity

Craftsmanship in Sukhuapada is more than just an economic activity; it is a vital part of the community's identity. The skills and knowledge associated with these crafts are a source of immense pride for the people of Sukhuapada, fostering a strong sense of belonging and continuity. The practice of these crafts creates a communal bond, as families and community members often work together, sharing techniques and stories.

This collective activity strengthens social cohesion and reinforces cultural norms and values. Additionally, the recognition and appreciation of their crafts by outsiders further enhance the community's self-esteem and solidarity. The preservation and promotion of these crafts are essential for maintaining the cultural fabric and social harmony of Sukhuapada.

c. Economic Importance

Despite the cultural richness and unique craftsmanship of Sukhuapada, the village's economy faces significant challenges. The economic benefits derived from the crafts are often limited, with many artisans struggling to earn a sustainable income. The sale of crafts provides some financial support, but mostly it is insufficient to ensure economic stability for the majority of artisans. Due to modernity, the limited market requirement for the traditional art, coupled with competition from mass-produced modern goods, has restricted the potential earnings from these traditional crafts. Moreover, inconsistent availability of raw materials and lack of modern marketing skills further impede economic growth. While efforts are being made to promote Sukhuapada as a cultural tourism destination, these initiatives are still in their nascent stages and have yet to generate substantial economic impact. To improve the economic situation, it is crucial to develop better marketing strategies, enhance access to broader markets, and provide training in modern business practices. Additionally, creating sustainable supply chains for raw materials and fostering collaborations with designers and brands can help increase the value and appeal of Sukhuapada's crafts, potentially boosting the village's economy in the long term.

Research Significance

a. Preservation of Indigenous Knowledge

Sukhuapada serves as a crucial repository of indigenous knowledge and skills, providing researchers with a wealth of information on indigenous sculpting art and crafts. The village's artisans possess expertise in stone sculpting which has its own historical and cultural significance. Researchers can study these techniques and skills to document and analyse the evolution of these crafts, ensuring that this knowledge is not lost.

b. Ethnographic Studies

This village serves as a rich platform for ethnographic studies, allowing researchers to explore the social and cultural dynamics of a community deeply-rooted in traditional practices. By observing and interacting with the artisans, researchers can gain insights into the community's way of life, social structures, and cultural values. This contributes to a broader understanding of how traditional crafts shape and are shaped by the community's identity.

c. Sustainable Practices

Sukhuapada’s artisans often use locally sourced, natural materials and employ sustainable techniques in their crafts. Researching these practices can provide valuable insights into sustainable living and resource management. This knowledge is particularly relevant in the context of global efforts to promote sustainability and environmental conservation.

Educational Value

a. Experiential Learning

Sukhuapada offers a unique setting for experiential learning, where students and educators can engage directly with artisans to learn traditional crafts (Fig.3). Workshops and hands-on training sessions will provide an immersive learning experience that goes beyond theoretical knowledge. This approach will help students develop a deeper appreciation for intangible heritage and traditional skills (Hooper-Greenhill, 2007).

b. Interdisciplinary Studies

The village’s rich cultural and artisanal heritage provides a fertile ground for interdisciplinary studies. Students and researchers from academic background such as anthropology, history, art, design, and environmental studies can collaborate to explore various aspects of Sukhuapada’s crafts and community life. This interdisciplinary approach will foster a holistic understanding of the interplay between culture, art, and society.

c. Skill Development

Learning traditional crafts in Sukhuapada can enhance students’ practical skills and creativity. By working alongside skilled artisans, students can acquire hands-on experience in techniques and skills that can be valuable in various professional fields, including art, design, and cultural conservation.

d. Cultural Exchange

Educational programmes in Sukhuapada facilitate cultural exchange, allowing students and visitors to gain a global perspective on indigenous art forms. This exchange will enrich the learning experience and promote mutual respect and understanding between different cultures. It will also help to raise awareness about the importance of preserving traditional crafts worldwide (Sharma, 2023).

Challenges and Opportunities

a. Documentation and Dissemination: One of the key challenges in preserving Sukhuapada’s craft heritage is the documentation and dissemination of traditional knowledge. Researchers and educators must work together to create comprehensive

records of techniques, materials, and cultural contexts. Digital archiving and publishing can help make this information accessible to a wider audience.

- b. Revitalizing Interest:** To sustain the village's crafts, it is essential to revitalize interest among the younger generation. Educational initiatives should focus on integrating traditional crafts into modern curricula and promoting them as viable career options. Collaborations with design schools and cultural institutions can help bridge the gap between tradition and contemporary relevance.
- c. Funding and Resources:** Securing adequate funding and resources for research and educational programmes is a persistent challenge. Partnerships with governmental and non-governmental organizations, as well as private sponsors, are crucial for supporting these initiatives. Investment in infrastructure, such as workshops and learning centres, can significantly enhance the educational experience.

Conclusion

Sukhuapada Crafts Village stands as a vital resource for research and education, offering valuable insights on traditional knowledge, sustainable practices, and cultural preservation. By leveraging the village's unique environment for experiential learning and interdisciplinary studies, researchers and educators can contribute to the safeguarding of this intangible heritage. Addressing these challenges requires innovative approaches, such as diversifying revenue streams, embracing digital transformation, and fostering partnerships with community organizations and educational institutions (Black, 2012). Continued efforts in documentation, revitalising interest, and securing resources are essential to ensure that Sukhuapada remains a living museum for posterity to learn from and appreciate.

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Figure 1. Artisan working in his natural habitat, Sukhuapada village, Odisha.

Figure 2. Artisan working on an intricate carving.

Figure 3. Author's hands-on sculpting training from local artists at Sukhuapada.